

2
0
2
5

№ 1

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy,
innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid
ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

- 05.01.00 – Axborot texnologiyalari, boshqaruv va kompyuter grafikasi
- 05.01.01 – Muhandislik geometriyasi va kompyuter grafikasi. Audio va video texnologiyalari
- 05.01.02 – Tizimli tahlil, boshqaruv va axborotni qayta ishlash
- 05.01.03 – Informatikaning nazariy asoslari
- 05.01.04 – Hisoblash mashinalari, majmualari va kompyuter tarmoqlarining matematik va dasturiy ta'minoti
- 05.01.05 – Axborotlarni himoyalash usullari va tizimlari. Axborot xavfsizligi
- 05.01.06 – Hisoblash texnikasi va boshqaruv tizimlarining elementlari va qurilmalari
- 05.01.07 – Matematik modellashtirish
- 05.01.11 – Raqamli texnologiyalar va sun'iy intellekt
- 05.02.00 – Mashinasozlik va mashinashunoslik
- 05.02.08 – Yer usti majmualari va uchish apparatlari
- 05.03.02 – Metrologiya va metrologiya ta'minoti
- 05.04.01 – Telekommunikatsiya va kompyuter tizimlari, telekommunikatsiya tarmoqlari va qurilmalari. Axborotlarni taqsimlash
- 05.05.03 – Yorug'lik texnikasi. Maxsus yoritish texnologiyasi
- 05.05.05 – Issiqlik texnikasining nazariy asoslari
- 05.05.06 – Qayta tiklanadigan energiya turlari asosidagi energiya qurilmalari
- 05.06.01 – To'qimachilik va yengil sanoat ishlab chiqarishlari materialshunosligi
- 05.08.03 – Temir yo'l transportini ishlatish
- 05.09.01 – Qurilish konstruksiyalari, bino va inshootlar
- 05.09.04 – Suv ta'minoti. Kanalizatsiya. Suv havzalarini muhofazalovchi qurilish tizimlari

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Elektron nashr,
185 sahifa, yanvar, 2025-yil.

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

BOSH MUHARRIR:

Zokirova Nodira Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

BOSH MUHARRIR O'RINBOSARI:

Shakarov Zafar G'afforovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, PhD

TAHRIR HAY'ATI:

Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, akademik

Sharipov Kongratbay Avazimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Maxkamov Baxtiyor Shuxratovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shaumarov Said Sanatovich, texnika fanlari doktori, professor

Turayev Bahodir Xatamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Nasimov Dilmurod Abdulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Allayeva Gulchexra Jalgasovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Arabov Nurali Uralovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Maxmudov Odiljon Xolmirzayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Xamrayeva Sayyora Nasimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bobonazarova Jamila Xolmurodovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Irmatova Aziza Baxromovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Bo'taboyev Muhammadjon To'ychiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor

Shamshiyeva Nargizaxon Nosirxuja kizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, professor, TDIU kengash kotibi

Xolmuxamedov Muhsinjon Murodullayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Xodjayeva Nodiraxon Abdurashidovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Amanov Otabek Amankulovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Qurbonov Samandar Pulatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Zikriyoyev Aziz Sadulloyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Tabayev Azamat Zaripbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sxay Lana Aleksandrovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent

Ismoilova Gulnora Fayzullayevna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Djumaniyazov Umrbek Ilxamovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kasimova Nargiza Sabitdjanovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent

Kalanova Moxigul Baxritdinovna, dotsent

Ashurzoda Luiza Muxtarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Sardor Begmaxmat o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sharipov Botirali Roxataliyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor

Tursunov Ulug'bek Sativoldiyevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dots.nt

Bauyetdinov Majit Janizaqovich, Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti dotsenti, PhD

Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li, Texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)

Sultonov Shavkatjon Abdullayevich, Kimyo fanlari doktori, (DSc)

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

Ma'lumot uchun, OAK
Rayosatining 2024-yil
28-avgustdagi 360/5-son
qarori bilan "Dissertatsiyalar
asosiy ilmiy natijalarini chop
etishga tavsiya etilgan milliy
ilmiy nashrlar ro'yxati"ga
texnika va iqtisodiyot fanlari
bo'yicha "Muhandislik va
iqtisodiyot" jurnali ro'yxatga
kiritilgan.

Muassis: "Tadbirkor va ishbilarmon" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz:

- Toshkent shahridagi G. V. Plexanov nomidagi Rossiya iqtisodiyot universiteti
- Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti
- Toshkent irrigatsiya va qishloq xo'jaligini mexanizatsiyalash muhandislari instituti" milliy tadqiqot universiteti
- Islom Karimov nomidagi Toshkent davlat texnika universiteti
- Muhammad al-Xorazmiy nomidagi Toshkent axborot texnologiyalari universiteti
- Toshkent davlat transport universiteti
- Toshkent arxitektura-qurilish universiteti
- Toshkent kimyo-texnologiya universiteti
- Jizzax politexnika instituti

MUNDARIJA

Milliy iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda xorijiy investitsiyalarni jalb etishning mazmun-mohiyati va nazariy asoslari.....	16
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li	
Muqobil energiyalarni tadqiq etish ilmiy – amaliy markazi.....	22
Mingyosharov Shahboz Sadillo o'g'li, Eshqulov Muhridin Urozboy o'g'li	
Ishlab chiqarish hisobining ayrim masalalari	28
Sidikov Nizomiddin G'ulomovich	
Совершенствование практики кредитования субъектов предпринимательства коммерческими банками.....	31
Джаббаров Алишер Кайимович	
Получение новых свойств соусов-паст за счёт добавления муки пророщенной крупы маш (vigna radiata)	37
Эрматов Отабек Сайитович, Холдоров Баходир Баратович, Додаев Кучкор Одилевич	
Ta'lim xizmatlari bozorida innovatsion marketing strategiyalardan foydalanish.....	41
Shaxobiddinova Malohat Zaynilobiddin qizi	
Transport vositalari sanoatini texnik transformatsiyalashda venchur iqtisodiyoti masalalari.....	47
Siddiqjanov Samandar Sohibjon o'g'li	
Исследование основные характеристики алюмосодержащие коагулянтов.....	53
Махмудов Мухтор Жамолович, Ҳайдаров Бекзоджон Абдумалик ўғли	
Kompressor stansiyalarda gaz haydash agregatlarining ishini optimallashtirish.....	62
Umarov Alixan Axmadovich	
Исследования условия процесса получения дорожных битумов на основе нефтяного сырья.....	75
Хужакулов Азиз Файзуллаевич, Абдуллаева Шохиста Шухратовна	
O'zbekistonda turistlarga ovqatlanish xizmatlarini ko'rsatishni rivojlantirishning boshqaruv mexanizmini takomillashtirish	81
Maxmadiyeva Charos Xayrullayevna	
Tijorat banklari tizimi barqarorligining nazariy asoslari.....	85
N.Q.Xolov	
G'o'zaning yangi tizmalarini tola sifati ko'rsatkichlari bo'yicha baholash.....	90
Boltaboev Xusniddin Abdig'anievich	
Sug'oriladigan tomorqa xo'jaligida yerdan foydalanishning xorij tajribalari.....	94
Haydarov Zafar Qahramonovich	
Энергоэффективность промышленности в современных условиях: концептуализация понятия и эмпирический анализ	99
Хамдамова Гавхар Абсаматовна	
Milliy korporativ boshqaruv tizimini xalqaro standartlar va zamonaviy ilg'or amaliyot asosida rivojlantirish.....	106
Ergashev Axmadjon Maxmudjon o'g'li, Mirobidov Mirzohid Yaxyoyevich	
Axborotlarni uzatishda tarmoqqa bo'ladigan tahdidlar.....	111
Sayidov Nozimjon Abdulnosirovich, Burhanova Zulhumor Odiljon qizi	
Namangan viloyat iqtisodiyotida mehnat resurslarini shakllantirish va ulardan foydalanish samaradorligini oshirish.....	117
Shermatov G'ofurjon G'ulamovich, Marupova Mohina Abduvoyit qizi	

Fuqarolik jamiyati institutlarini qo'llab-quvvatlashda davlat subsidiyasining o'rni.....	122
Xusanov Otabek Nishonovich	
Перспективы внедрения исламских финансовых продуктов в узбекистане.....	128
Абдувосидова Гуландом Абдурашид кизи	
Tadbirkorlik subyektlari faoliyatida xalqaro standartlarni joriy etish metodologiyasi	135
Oqboyev Alisher Rasuljanovich	
Davlat xaridlarida narx differensial indeks: o'zbekiston amaliyotida regressiyaviy tahlil va iqtisodiy xulosalar.....	140
Majidov Nizom Baxramovich	
Mahalliy budjetlar moliyaviy mustaqilligini ta'minlashning ilg'or xorij tajribasi va undan O'zbekistonda foydalanish istiqbollari	146
Kudaybergenova Guzal	
Raqamlashtirish sharoitida tijorat banklarning depozit operatsiyalarini takomillashrish.....	151
Xudayarov Oybek Odilovich	
Mamlakatning eksport-import salohiyatini oshirish asosida barqaror iqtisodiy o'sishni ta'minlash	157
Raximov Eshmurod Normuradovich	
O'zbekiston respublikasi qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyotida investitsiyadan samarali foydalanish.....	163
Elboyeva Shaxzoda Olim qizi	
Sanoat korxonalarida tashqi iqtisodiy faoliyatini moliyaviy salohiyatini ta'minlash mexanizmi	168
Jalolov Ilhomjon Isomiddinovich	
Xizmat ko'rsatish korxonalarida resurslardan oqilona foydalanish yo'llari	176
Seytnazarov Berdibek Ametbekovich	
Public-private partnership: essence, functions and world practice	179
Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltabayevna	

PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP: ESSENCE, FUNCTIONS AND WORLD PRACTICE

Ataniyazova Maksuda Baltabayevna

Head of the Department of General Economic Sciences,
Tashkent University of Applied Sciences, Tashkent, Uzbekistan
ORCID: 0009-0000-9403-6693

Abstract: The article examines the essence, objectives and world experience of using one of the modern systems of a market economy - the public-private partnership mechanism - in the implementation of infrastructure projects. This article examines the practice of creating a regulatory framework for state associations and organizations, the purpose of which is to form and maintain stable relations between state bodies and private entrepreneurship in the provision of public services. The experience of working with this mechanism in the European Union, the USA and the BRICS countries is analyzed, and current trends in the development of public-private partnership in the modern world are identified.

Keywords: public-private partnership, concession, infrastructure projects, regulatory framework, world practice, public-private partnership institution, investment policy.

Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada bozor iqtisodiyotining zamonaviy tizimlaridan biri bo'lgan davlat-xususiy sheriklik mexanizmining infratuzilma loyihalarini amalga oshirishdagi mohiyati, maqsadlari va jahon tajribasi o'rganilgan. Ushbu maqolada davlat organlari va xususiy tadbirkorlik o'rtasida jamoat xizmatlarini taqdim etishda barqaror aloqalarni shakllantirish va saqlab qolish maqsadida davlat uyushmalari va tashkilotlarini tartibga soluvchi normativ-huquqiy baza yaratish amaliyoti o'rganilgan. Ushbu mexanizm bilan ishlash tajribasi Yevropa Ittifoqi, AQSh va BRICS mamlakatlarida tahlil qilingan va zamonaviy dunyoda davlat-xususiy sheriklikni rivojlantirishdagi joriy tendensiyalar aniqlangan.

Kalit so'zlar: davlat-xususiy sheriklik, koncessiya, infratuzilma loyihalari, normativ-huquqiy baza, jahon tajribasi, davlat-xususiy sheriklik instituti, investitsiya siyosati.

Аннотация: В статье рассматриваются сущность, цели и мировой опыт использования одного из современных механизмов рыночной экономики – механизма государственно-частного партнерства – в реализации инфраструктурных проектов. В статье изучена практика создания нормативно-правовой базы для государственных объединений и организаций, целью которых является формирование и поддержание стабильных отношений между государственными органами и частным предпринимательством в предоставлении общественных услуг. Анализируется опыт работы с данным механизмом в Европейском Союзе, США и странах БРИКС, а также выявляются текущие тенденции в развитии государственно-частного партнерства в современном мире.

Ключевые слова: государственно-частное партнерство, концессия, инфраструктурные проекты, нормативно-правовая база, мировой опыт, институт государственно-частного партнерства, инвестиционная политика.

INTRODUCTION

Various forms, mechanisms and directions of using public-private partnerships allow solving strategic tasks - from the creation and development of infrastructure to the development and implementation of new projects. In this regard, public-private partnerships (PPPs) have gained particular importance in recent years. Based on this, in this article, the relevance of studying the methods, forms and mechanisms of public-private partnerships in modern conditions, in particular, the best practices of foreign countries, is increasing.

In order for the state to effectively implement PPP programs, it is important to improve the regulatory framework, create special institutions to support public-private partnerships, and develop financial support mechanisms.

In this context, in order to regulate relations in the field of public-private partnerships, including concessions, The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No¹. URQ-537 «On Public-Private Partnerships» of May 10, 2019 was adopted.

According to the law, a public-private partnership is a legally formalized cooperation between a public partner and a private partner for a certain period of time, based on the pooling of their resources to implement a public-private partnership project [1].

PPP in the provision of public services is currently developing rapidly in countries around the world, including our republic, and demonstrates the enormous economic potential in this area. In this regard, the problem of defining the essence of public-private partnership and its tasks in the economy is becoming urgent.

The objectives of this study are:

- to study the essence and content of public-private partnerships from an institutional and economic perspective;
- determine its functions in the modern economy;
- study the practice of using PPPs around the world;
- to identify current trends in the development of PPPs in the modern world.

In most cases, public-private partnership is understood as “a system of mutual cooperation between business and government in the construction, reconstruction and modernization of infrastructure facilities” [2, p. 191].

However, in our opinion, public-private partnerships meet all the characteristics of an institution, both in terms of content and in terms of the tasks it performs.

LITERATURE REVIEW OF THE SUBJECT

Published abroad and in our country In economic literature, the characteristics of the development of partnership relations between the state and the private sector, models for the effective implementation of the public-private partnership mechanism in the world, and the scope and directions of using public-private partnership in developed and developing countries have been extensively studied by economists from a scientific, theoretical and methodological perspective.

According to the foreign scholar E.R. Yeascombe, who was one of the first to extensively study public-private partnerships in the world, «PPP is an alternative form of public procurement (public procurement) of infrastructure facilities by the public sector, financed by state debt or tax revenues» [3]. In this definition, the foreign scholar assumes that PPP is financed mainly from the state budget.

Foreign economist J.K. Galbraith [4, pp. 200-250] in his work partnership between the state and business, formation of investment funds, public-private partnership He has researched areas such as the conceptual foundations of.

Public-private partnerships scientific and theoretical foundations of, issues of regulating private investments, Problems related to the conditions for using the economic functions of the state to form a competitive environment JM Keynes [5], Y.A. Schumpeter [6], J.Pear, J.G.Peters [7] illuminated in the centuries.

1 <https://lex.uz/docs/-4329270>

Russian scientists VG Varnavsky, [8, pp. 45-85], V.A. Kabashkin [9, pp. 15-18], ED Frolova [10, pp. 31-32] and others study the formation of a system of economic relations between the public and private sectors, the economic essence and content of the category of «public-private partnership», goals and objectives, structure and models. Areas related to state and public property have been studied.

Local economists S. E. The studies of Elmiraev, N. Sh. Shavkatov [11], G. Utemuradova [12] and S. Yunusova [13] examine the experiences of public-private partnerships and the prospects for their application in our country. The main forms of public-private partnerships have been studied.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Economic research methods such as studying the foreign experience of public-private partnerships conducted by world scientists and economists, collecting data, analyzing and synthesizing the collected data, and logical thinking were widely used.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In order to properly establish cooperation between the state and the private sector, it is important to rely on the experience of foreign countries. Currently, developing countries, in particular, Uzbekistan, also envisage strengthening cooperation between the state and the private sector in the development and regulation of socio-economic infrastructure. In this regard, it is important to use the vast experience of developed countries in the effective implementation of the PPP mechanism in these processes and introduce their corresponding models in the practice of our republic.

The public-private partnership structure includes:

- rules for cooperation between business entities and the government in the economic sphere;
- addressees of the rules – government and business structures;
- legislation on public-private partnerships, which determines the mechanism for ensuring compliance with the rules and is a guarantee of their implementation. Consequently, public-private partnerships have all the characteristics of a formal institution in terms of content and structure. Does a public-private partnership have the functional characteristics of an institution, that is, does it perform functions similar to institutions?

It is known that institutions perform coordination, dissemination, information and constraint functions [14]. In our opinion, public-private partnerships perform all of the above functions because:

- allows business entities and government bodies to coordinate their actions in the economic sphere;
- regulates the use of state economic resources by business entities;
- affects the movement of economic resources between economic entities;
- forms a set of possible business decisions;
- The economic essence of the institution of public-private partnership is expressed in its performance of an optimization function, which consists in the most effective distribution of the risks of economic activity and the allocation of resources of society as a whole.

Public-private partnerships have a rich history. The first canal construction on a concession basis in France dates back to 1552. Subsequent public-private partnership projects have already had a larger scale. In Britain, state privileges were granted to private companies in the 17th and 18th centuries. - The famous East India Company, which was engaged in the management of colonies in India and other countries of the British Crown, was essentially a concession [5]. At the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, during the period of intensive construction of railways and the development of the steel industry, many countries, including Russia, actively used the model of concession agreements. The Eiffel Tower was built in this way. Later, various forms of public-private partnerships were used to restore local infrastructure in post-war Europe.

In the 1990s, a qualitatively new stage in the development of public-private partnerships began in Europe, in which a modern concept of such cooperation was formed. The regulatory and legal framework for the development of public-private partnerships in the European Union is the “Green Book on Public-Private Partnerships” [1]. In this law, “the concept of public-private partnership means

forms of cooperation between state bodies and the private sector to achieve state goals, in which the necessary resources are jointly managed and the project risks are appropriately distributed between project partners. “[5, p. 191].

The British system, in particular the experience of the Partnership UK public-private company, established through the Private Finance Initiative program of the John Major government, has made a significant contribution to the development of the PPP mechanism in Europe.

Partnership UK, a special public-private company established in 2000 by the Treasury Working Group, is 51% owned by the private sector in the form of private equity funds and banks and 49% by the British and Scottish governments. Partnership UK works with public authorities as an advisor, assessor and developer of public-private partnership projects. The main objective of Partnership UK is to create and systematize new tools for cooperation and to standardize existing contracts between public authorities and private companies. This organization also helps to create similar structures in other countries: Portugal Parública, Canada Partnership BC, Infrastructure Ontario, etc. were created with the help of Partnership UK [2].

European Union countries create their own state organizations with similar functions. For example, the Spanish SEITT agency, the German Partnerschaft Deutschland organization, etc.

Today, the European Union countries have the most developed regulatory and practical framework for regulating the field of public-private partnerships, which has already gone beyond the borders of one state and spread throughout Europe. Directive 2004/18/EC and Directive 2004/17/EC regulate public-private partnerships in the field of public contracts for water and energy supply, transport, and the supply of goods and services [7; 8]. The Green Paper on Public-Private Partnerships is the only methodological framework in the field of public-private partnerships in the European Union.

The experience of PPPs in the United States also has a much longer history, during which the concept of a public-private partnership was developed as a contract in which a private company is allowed to participate in public property in an agreed and approved manner, as well as perform functions that are traditionally the responsibility of the government.

The United States has created many mechanisms and institutions that contribute to the rapid development of public-private partnership practices, but the leading role belongs to the National Council on Public-Private Partnerships (NCPMP).

Its main tasks include providing information on PPPs, ensuring contacts between the private sector and public authorities, educational activities and removing obstacles to the implementation of public-private partnership projects. The members of the Council include 130 private organizations and government representatives, including Bank of America Merrill Lynch, Deloitte, Parsons, the Public-Private Partnership Department, the District of Columbia. The private sector representatives are companies that occupy leading positions in their industries and have extensive experience in implementing PPP projects, and the government representatives are specialized institutions and departments of seven states on public-private partnerships [3].

However, the American model has serious limitations. First, PPP projects are implemented only by American contractors. Thus, the participation of foreign investors in public-private partnership projects in the United States remains practically non-existent. Second, not all states have a single legislative framework for public-private partnerships, which creates institutional and political obstacles.

As a result, judging by the US experience, partnerships are often created and regulated at the city level, where projects in the field of road construction and utilities predominate.

The development of public-private partnership practices is hindered by the lack of unified legislation and limited opportunities for foreign investors.

The BRICS countries are showing positive dynamics in the development and application of public-private partnerships. China's practice of attracting large investments through PPPs has been ongoing since the early 2000s. and is regulated by two main laws, namely: «On Government Procurement of the People's Republic of China» and «Conclusion of the State Council» [9].

The spread of public-private partnerships in Brazil is facilitated by the National Privatization Program and Concession Law (No. 8,987 of February 13, 1995) and the Public-Private Partnership Law No. 11,079 of 2004 [10]. They are the basis for private investor participation in public property.

At the same time, the Brazilian regulatory framework is built on the principle of public participation in infrastructure development when necessary and when there are no other alternatives.

The main goal of using public-private partnerships in India is to increase capital efficiency while maintaining a balance of interests between government agencies and private businesses.

The first regulatory legal framework for public-private partnerships is the current Partnerships Act No. 9 of 25 April 1872 [11]. The Constitution obliges each state in India to establish a municipal corporation for each sector: roads and bridges, utilities, water supply, etc. The municipal corporation, in turn, has the right to enter into concession agreements with private sector enterprises. To attract investors to large infrastructure projects, the Indian government has introduced a subsidized financing system, under which projects with low capital efficiency receive subsidies in the amount of 20% of the total capital investment from a specially created Infrastructure Development Fund [5].

The practice of public-private partnerships in South Africa was initiated by Section 217 of the Constitution of South Africa [12]. Public-private partnerships are regulated by the Public Finance Management Act (1999) [13].

In conclusion, most public-private partnership projects in the BRICS countries are implemented under the "Build-Own-Transfer" model, which allows member countries and corporations to make mutual investments. However, there is currently no higher legal framework in this space that goes beyond the national framework that standardizes projects, as is the case with the experience of the European Union countries.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it is worth noting that in the modern world, the institution of public-private partnership is becoming increasingly widespread, becoming the basis for the implementation of various projects at all levels of government.

Two different trends can be distinguished in the development of the institution of public-private partnership:

- formation of a legal framework (currently regional) that is superior to the national one (the example of the European Union);
- the fact that the national legal framework for this institution was not formed quickly enough in a number of countries.

The first trend is typical for developed countries and contributes to the acceleration of the development and spread of this institution and the solution of important problems facing society. The second, which limits the formation and development of the institution of public-private partnership, is typical for developing countries. In general, we can conclude that the institution of public-private partnership has a high potential for solving national economic problems and it is necessary to encourage its development at a national and supranational level, in particular, at least at the level of the Central Asian Republics.

References

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. LRUz-537 "On Public-Private Partnership" dated May 10, 2019 <https://lex.uz/docs/4329270>
2. Belyuchenko, A. V. Implementation of infrastructural projects: international experience and Russian practice / A. V. Belyuchenko // Stage: economic theory, analysis, practice. – 2011. – No. 6. – S. 95–100.
3. Gosudarstvenno-chastnoe partnership: basic principles of financing / E. R. Yescombe; Per. English–M.: Alpina Publisher, 2015.–457 pp. P. 24.
4. Galbraith, Dj.K. Ekonomicheskie teorii i tseli obshchestva = Economics and the Public Purpose (1973) / Pod obshch. ed. i s predisl. N. N. Inozemtseva, A. G. Mileykovsky. - M.:Progress, 1976. – 408 p.
5. Keynes Dj.M. Obshchaya theory zanyatosti, protsenta i deneg / Per. sangl. prof. N.N. Lyubimova, pod. ed. d.e.n., prof. L.P. Kurakova. - Moscow: MIEMP, 2010.

6. Schumpeter J.A. History of economic analysis v 3 tt. - SPb.: Economic School, 2004.
7. Peters JG, Pierre J. Governance Politics and the State (Political Analysis). - New York, 2000.
8. Varnavsky V.G., Klimenko A.V., Korolev V.A. Gosudarstvenno-chastnoe partnership: theory and practice: uchebnoe posobie. - M.: GU-VShE, 2010.
9. Kabashkin V.A. Formirovaniye i razvitiye partnerskikh otnosheniy gosudarstva i predprinimatelskikh struktur v Rossiyskoi Federatsii (administrative aspect): autoref.. dis. dr. economy nauk:08.00.05/ V.A. Kabashkin.- M., 2007. - S. 23.
10. Frolova E.D. Osnovnye tendentsii razvitiya vzaimootnosheniy gosudarstva i biznesa/ E.D. Frolova // Vestnik UGTU-UI. - 2003. - No. 7. - S. 31.
11. Elmirzaev SE, Shavkatov N.Sh. Advanced foreign experiences of public-private partnership relations and prospects for their application in our country. // Scientific electronic journal «International Finance and Accounting». No. 3, June, 2019.
12. Utemuratova GX Improving the methodological foundations of the development of public-private partnership in the service sector. Dissertation abstract. 2023.
13. Yunusova SB State-Advanced foreign experiences in implementing infrastructure projects based on private partnerships. // Scientific journal «Economy and Education». / Issue 1, 2023, Pages 522-530. https://doi.org/10.55439/ECED/vol24_iss1/a82
14. Sazanova, S. L. Institutional theory of organization / S.L. Sazanova // Vestnik University. – 2015. – No. 8. – S. 61–67.
15. Cheremnaya, T. S. Gosudarstvenno-chastnoe partnership v stranax BRICS: opyt i perspektivy realizatsii / T. S. Cheremnaya // Vestnik universiteta MGIMO. – 2015. – No. 5 (44). - S. 190–197.
16. Green Paper on Public-Private Partnerships and Community Law on Public Contracts and Concessions. Commission of the European Communities. Brussels, 30.04.2004 [Electronic resource]. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM:l22012>.
17. Directive 2004/18 // EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Communities of March 31, 2004 [Electronic resource]. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:32004L0018>.
18. Directive 2004/17 // EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of the European Union of March 31, 2004 [Electronic resource]. <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/ALL/?uri=celex%3A32004L0017>.
19. Government Procurement Law of the People's Republic of China, June 29, 2002 [Electronic resource]. <http://www.people.com.cn/GB/shehui/43/20020710/772676.html>.
20. General Law of Permits and Concessions of Public Services (Federal Law No. 8,987 of 1995) [Electronic resource]. <https://www.loc.gov/law/help/govt-procurement-law/brazil.php>.
21. The Law on Contracts No. 9 of April 25, 1872 [Electronic resource]. <http://chdistrictcourts.gov.in/the%20indian%20contract%20act.pdf>.
22. Constitution of the Republic of South Africa, 1996 [Electronic resource]. <https://cer.org.za/virtual-library/legislation/national/constitutional/constitution-of-the-republic-of-south-africa-1996>.
23. Public finance management act No. 1 of 1999. Ministry of finance of South Africa 02.03.1999 [Electronic resource]. <http://www.treasury.gov.za/legislation/PFMA/PFMA%201999%20as%20amended%20March%202017.pdf>.

Muhandislik va Iqtisodiyot

ijtimoiy-iqtisodiy, innovatsion texnik,
fan va ta'limga oid ilmiy-amaliy jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz Hakimov

Musahhih: Zokir Alibekov

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Oloviddin Sobir o'g'li

2025. № 1

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

"Muhandislik va iqtisodiyot" jurnali 26.06.2023-yildan
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi
Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan
№S-5669245 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.
Litsenziya raqami: №095310.

**Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahri Yunusobod
tumani 15-mavze 19-uy**

